

Improving Gender Classification Using Huge Image Database with Deep Learning-Based Model

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ABSTRACT

Human gender classification received huge attention because of its diverse applications in various domains such as human-computer interaction (HCI) and computer-aided technology. It has previously been studied using various visual and machine learning algorithms but existing methods still face challenges for varying ages and ethnic groups. In order to meet this challenge, we take a step to improve our proposed model performance using a huge custom-built clean image database. In this paper, we recommend using a custom huge human face database to train the neural network-based model that can improve the gender classification accuracy of diverse ethnic groups. Thus, we prepared a huge gender image database of 200 thousand of images to enhance the performance of the proposed gender classification model. We cleaned and preprocessed the dataset to improve and speed up the model training procedure. The experimental outcome shows the highest accuracy of 95.7% with 98% confidence in the gender classification of an individual image.

Keywords: Gender classification; visual methods; image database; convolution neural network; feature extraction; image filters; fully connected layers; soft max classifier.

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INTRODUCTION

Gender classification deals with the problem of automatically detecting a person's gender from visual data that consists of still photos, video footage, depth maps, and other sources. The technique can be used in various applications including face authentication, security systems, voice synthesis, and video dubbing.

Face detection research received immense attention in the field of computer vision. Consequently, its subfields of age and gender estimation got to focus and various researchers have been working on these areas to achieve better and better performance. The gender classification becomes challenging with varying age and ethnic groups, other influential aspects are camera viewpoint, facial expression, and human pose that disturb the model performance.

Convolutional neural networks (CNN) emerged from the existing learning techniques and improved gender classification accuracy remarkably. But aging and race make gender classification not only difficult even for human but also an open research area. Its classification accuracy may affect the age estimation too, See Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Sample Face Images Collected from Various Online Sources, Especially Kaggle Image Datasets.

The rest of the paper is laid out as follows. We present an overview of related literature in section II. In section III, we discuss in detail the proposed methodology. We present the experiments and results in section IV. Section V summarizes the proposed methodology and the way forward for future work to improve the limitations of the proposed method.

RELATED WORK

Before going into the details of the proposed method, we briefly go through the existing gender classification methods especially considering the sophisticated neural network techniques that helped to improve gender classification. Finally, we conclude the section by discussing our contribution to the field.

Visual-Based Methods

The first study on gender classification [1, 2] was conducted in the early 1990s. Faces were manually aligned for the experiments, and both of them utilized multilayer neural networks.

Rai and Khanna [3] claimed that extracting essential aspects from the face using both wavelet and random transform approaches may effectively classify gender. After detecting faces, the data is reduced by using the random and wavelet transforms to extract the essential aspects of the face. The Daubechies (db3) wavelet filter is used to compute an image projection and decompose each image's random space up to a third level with the random transform. The output of db3 was a feature vector that was fed into the K-nearest neighbor (k-NN) classifier.

Nazir et al. [4] lowered the dimensions to make the processing faster by utilizing the Viola Jones technique to detect the face from an image. They used histogram equalization to restore the image lighting impact to its original state. ACE (automated color equalization) image has certain prominent features which were obtained using the discrete cosine transformation (DCT) technique.

Jabid et al. [5] stated two techniques for gender classification. The appearance-based feature and geometric feature techniques. Edge response values were used to generate local directional patterns (LDP) coding. The appearance of the face is depicted using a strong local directional pattern. For classification, they employed a support vector machine (SVM), which seeks to locate the hyperplane for linearly separable problems.

Mozaffari et al. [6] proposed a method for merging geo-metric and appearance-based features of an image into a single image. The discrete cosine transformation (DCT) and the local binary pattern (LBP) are used to extract appearance-based features. The image is represented using the DCT coefficient, which reduces its size. The local binary pattern was used to describe texture for the first time. A woman's face is said to be longer and rounder than a man's face. It improves the ellipse's fit around the gender's face.

Azzopardi et al. [7] developed a technique for gender detection from facial images based on a fusion of SVM classifiers. The GENDER-FERET dataset [8] which includes expressions, face attributes, background, and illumination fluctuations, was used to evaluate the approach. The parameters used to train each classifier are the histogram of oriented gradients (HOG) (shape), LBP (texture), and raw pixel values. SVMs with a linear kernel was employed for the last two attributes, whereas SVMs with histogram intersection kernels were utilized for the first two.

Kumar et al. [9] presented a novel algorithm based on facial images for automatic live gender detection. SVM was used for classification, while the scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) descriptor was used for feature extraction. The FEI [10], the face image database was used to test the performance of the proposed method. A combination of shifted filter responses (COSFIRE) [11] were used to recognize patterns and detect key points.

Neural Network Techniques

In this section, we describe the existing technique based on the neural network models for gender classification. Bai et al. [12] proposed a multi-branch fully convolutional network (MB-FCN) for face classification. The MB-FCN detector can deal with faces at all scale ranges with just one pass across the backbone network. For each branch, the specific skip connections of the convolutional feature maps at different layers are used to display faces in specific scale ranges. Later, the MB-FCN detector was tested on two public face detection benchmarks, Fddb and WIDER FACE. MB-FCN uses a GPU to process images with a resolution of 640×480 pixels at 15 frames per second, with no assumptions regarding the minimum observable face size.

Dhomme et al. [13] developed the D-CNN approach as an effective approach for speeding up the detection process in real-time gender detection, and the VGGNet with celebrity dataset was then employed to obtain gender prediction accuracy.

Viedma et al. [14] presented a deep learning-based technique for automatic pixel feature extraction for gender categorization using near-infrared periocular iris images. To select the most relevant areas on periocular iris images, they used bottleneck, fine-tuning, and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained from scratch methodologies. The Data Augmentation technique was used to train a CNN from scratch with a minimal number of images, which achieved the classification rate and automatically selected the most relevant areas for this assignment.

Zeng et al. [15] proposed a proposal pyramid network (PPN) to quickly generate face candidates, reducing the computational complexity of cascaded DCNN face detectors. PPN is a multi-branch lightweight fully convolutional network that takes a single image as input and generates face proposals with different scales in terms of separate branches at the same time. A three-stage cascaded DCNN face detector based on PPN is implemented to test the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Khan et al. [16] proposed a unified framework for face image analysis through end-to-end semantic face segmentation. The proposed system incorporates a set of face understanding stack components, such as head posture estimation and gender recognition. The conditional random fields (CRFs) based segmentation algorithm is trained using a manually annotated face data set. A CRF-based multi-class face segmentation framework divides a facial picture into six pieces. For each class, a probabilistic classification approach is applied, and probability maps are generated. The probability maps are employed as feature descriptors, and each job is represented with a random decision forest (RDF) classifier (head pose, and gender).

Tapia et al. [17] proposed a 2D quadrature quaternionic filter and a selection of key features from normalized iris images for gender classification. They utilized the 1-D log-Gabor standard encoding approach, then encoded the phase information of the normalized images using 4 bits per pixel with a 2D-Gabor filter and selected the best bits from the four generated images (1 real and 3 imaginary).

Hassan et al. [18] proposed a method for determining gender using multiple convolutional neural networks (CNN). The suggested method contains five phases: face detection, background removal, face alignment, multiple CNN, and voting systems. For each network, it is used to extract various features. Mliki et al. [19] introduced a face detection method based on deep learning (CNN). The process includes generating a CNN architecture for face detection tasks that incorporates both global and local features at multiple scales. The architecture is made up of two main networks: a region proposal network that generates a list of regions of interest (RoIs), and a network that uses these RoIs for face/non-face classification. Both of them use a pre-trained ResNet-50 model with full image convolution.

Pre-trained CNN-based Models

In this sub-section, we discussed the pre-trained neural network models used for the gender classification study. Ranjan et al. [20] proposed a method called HyperFace for simultaneous facial recognition, pose prediction, and gender recognition using CNNs. This approach employs a separate CNN to merge the deep CNN's intermediate layers, followed by a multitasking learning algorithm on the fused features. HyperFace-ResNet is based on the ResNet-101 model to boost the algorithm speed. Arora et al. [21] proposed a convolutional neural network-based approach for determining gender from faces. The network is trained using back-propagation and Adam optimization. The CNN network performance is evaluated using convolution operations on the publicly accessible CASIA face recognition dataset [22].

Gender Image Database

We collected and prepared the human gender image database from various online and offline resources especially Kaggle repositories, the database consists of around 200k images of both male and female subjects, which occupies 1.3GB of disk size. Later, we segregated the male and female images and kept them in separate folders for further processing. We additionally crop the images to discard the unnecessary details and align them to correctly visible the face.

Preprocessing the Database

After gathering the dataset from diverse sources, preprocessing and normalizing the image database becomes the necessary step. First, we wrote a programming script to bring all the images to a common image format .PNG followed by the resize method to change the random data points dimensions to the 224×224. We further crop and smooth the images to suppress the noise, see Fig. 1.

Network Architecture

In this section, we discuss in detail the network architecture of the proposed model. The network is divided into two subsections, feature extraction, and image classification.

Feature Extraction Phase

We used convolutional and max-pooling layers of the network to extract features from the input images. The images pass through five convolution layers that form the network with Conv2D, it consists of 32, 64, 64, 128, and 128 filters followed by max-pooling layers. Each convolutional layer is backed up by the ReLU activation function and batch normalization. The convolution and ReLU layers are applied twice before applying the pooling layer. The max-pooling layer reduces the spatial dimension from 96×96 to 32 × 32 by using a 3 × 3 pool size.

This operation of multiple convolutional and ReLU layers allows learning a richer set of features. Here, we increased the filter size from 32 to 64 and finally to 128 to learn the complex combination of patterns in the dataset. The max pooling size is decreased from 3 × 3 to 2 × 2 so that spatial dimensions do not get reduced quickly, see Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Proposed network architecture. The first stage extracts the features using various filters in the convolutional layers. The classification stage consists of fully connected layers to learn the features to classify the gender.

Classification Phase

After extracting features, we flat ten the input image data and feed it to the classification stage of the proposed network. The classification phase consists of the fully connected layers to learn the extracted features. We introduced two fully connected layers with one additional layer for the output. ReLU and batch normalization with Dense (1024) defines the fully connected layer where dropout is applied for the regularization. We dropped out 50% of the nodes during the training.

First fully connected layer consist of size 3200×256 with ReLU activation function whereas the second FC consists of size 256×1 with sigmoid activation function. Finally, we used the softmax classifier to receive the predicted probabilities for each class label, see Fig. 3.

Real-Time Gender Prediction

We used a huge custom-built image database to train our model. After the training phase, we stored the model in hdf5 format for real-time prediction. We used this model to classify the human gender. The experiments confirmed the improved results with the customized image database.

EXPERIMENTS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We conducted various challenging experiments to test the robustness of the proposed method. We carried out two experiments. In experiment I, we generated a small challenging database of 100 images based on varying ages and ethnic groups, the images in the database were independent and they were not presented to the model during the training or testing phase. Finally, in experiment II, we compared the proposed CNN-based custom model with the existing state-of-the-art CNN-based pre-trained models where our model outperformed other baseline models.

Experiment I: Testing with Small-Sized Database

In this experiment, we collected random images from the internet and offline resources and prepared an independent image database for testing the proposed method. The images were not used in the training or testing phase of the model. The testing image database included 100 images of various age groups of people from 0 to 60 to make the classification more challenging.

We conducted the training on the Google GPU to speed up the training process, whereas we tested the gender prediction both on the CPU and GPU. After the training phase, we saved and downloaded the model in hdf5 format and tested it locally on the CPU. The proposed method correctly classified 98 images out of 100 images that recorded 98% accuracy, see Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Experiment I: Proposed method tested with custom-built independent image database. The first row (a–d) shows male images with ages ranging from 25 to 60. The second row shows females images belonging to ages between 16 to 30. The method showed remarkable performance.

Experiment II Comparison with the Pre-Trained Models

We also tested the same dataset and facial features with other CNN-based pre-trained models but they did not show reasonable accuracy. The pre-trained models include ResNet50, Inception V3, and Xception. We considered the pre-trained models as baseline methods and compared the proposed method against them, the proposed method outperformed the baseline methods.

Our method showed 95.7%, ResNet-50 showed 95%, Inception v3 showed 92%, and finally, Xception showed 90% accuracy. Our method outperforms the baseline methods by 0.7%, 3.7%, and 5.7%, see TABLE I.

Table I: Experiment II: Comparison of the Proposed Method with the Baseline CNN-Based Pre-Trained Models RESNET50, INCEPTION V3, and XCEPTION.

Models	Accuracy (%)
CNN	95.7
ResNet 50	95.0
Inception v3	92.0
Xception	90.0

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a customized CNN-based model and prepared an image database of 200k data points to achieve improved gender classification accuracy. We gathered, prepared, and processed a huge gender-based dataset for better model training that improved the results. The model is well set to classify the challenging dataset of gender based on varying ages and ethnic groups. We also experimented with other pre-trained models to examine and compare their performance with the proposed method. The proposed method clearly outperformed the baseline methods significantly based on performance.

For future work, we have set a stage to extend our work to propose a robust age estimation algorithm integrated with gender classification. The extended work will contribute to the multimedia and imaging fields both in theory and application. The extended work will further contribute to the automation of the natural language processing (NLP) field of study where the classification of gender and age is an important step.

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